

REPORT OF THE PROJECT “FISM, FIGHTING WITH A SMILE: SATIRICAL AND HUMOURIST VOICES OF RESILIENCE FROM HINDI SUBALTERN SUBJECTS AND COMMUNITIES”¹

OBJECT: Creation of the official Website of the project FISM “Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Subaltern Subjects and Communities”.

Function of the Website

The European-funded FISM project entailed the realization of task 6.1., entitled “Creation and use of a Website”. The creation of the Website is part of the communication activities as envisaged in the project; it has the objective of communicating to the general public the objectives and main activities connected to the project. Moreover, it is also conceived as a platform that the PI could employ to facilitate contacts between writers, artists, scholars and stakeholders. The objective is, therefore, also that of encouraging new research in areas regarding the fields of humour and satire in India. To do this, the Website also hosts a Podcast where the PI will produce audiovisual contributions to explore arguments associated with the project. The Podcast will also host interviews to artists, writers and scholars. After the creation of the Website it will be used by the PI for communication purposes throughout the entire duration of the project.

Date of activation and management of the Website

The Website was activated on 20.10.2024. For the entire duration of the project, the PI intends to update the Website with new audiovisual materials.

Structure of the Website

The FISM Website is made up of the the following sections:

- 1) Homepage: these sections shows basic information about the name and objectives of the Website. It also clearly shows the Website to the FISM project.
- 2) Project page, where the PI clarifies the main objectives of the FISM project.
- 3) Researcher, which contains detailed information about the CV of the Principal Investigator.
- 4) Digital content, where the PI uploads all the audiovisual materials that they he intends to communicate to the general public. This section of the Website also hosts the Podcast.
- 5) News
- 6) Contacts.

Ethical aspects

This website is compliant with the GDPR regulation. Throughout the website creation process, the PI

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Call HORIZON-MSCA-2023-PF-01. Project 101152854. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or that of the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

respect criteria regarding gender equality and attempted to avoid any misrepresentation of the arts and/or the artists connected to the areas of humour and satire in the South Asian context. These criteria have also been followed in creating some of the pictures that have been added to the Website. These pictures are freely inspired by performative events connected to humorous and satirical traditions in India.

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Call HORIZON-MSCA-2023-PF-01.
Project 101152854. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the
author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or that
of the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the
granting authority can be held responsible for them.